

AUDIENCE PERCEPTION OF POLITICAL NEWS PROGRAMME PRESENTATION IN ARISE AND CHANNELS TELEVISIONS AMONG RESIDENTS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

Politics more often than not forms the greater part of the contents that media outlets present to the public. Because of political leanings or interests, politicians would always want the narratives to go in their favour. Hence, the tendency to influence the news contents and skew them in their favour, thus compromising objectivity. This study therefore sought to evaluate audience perception of political news handling in Arise and Channels Televisions. The study, which was anchored on Source Credibility and Perception Theories, was carried out using survey and in-depth interview methods. Respondents' responses from Enugu South, Enugu North, and Enugu East LGAs, which constitute Enugu metropolis were analysed to ascertain their perception on the handling of political news programmes by these two broadcast media organizations. A quantitative sample of three hundred and thirty (330) respondents was randomly selected for the study, using the Australian Calculator. Analysis of data indicated that Arise and Channels, in spite of daunting challenges are in most cases perceived by the audience as mostly objective, fair and balanced in their political news programmes. Consequently, it is recommended among others that the journalists in the two stations, especially those who handle political programmes, should continue to be firm in their political news handling and in adhering to the professional ethics of journalism and being socially responsible in their news programmes. It is also recommended that they try to resist any attempt especially by the political class to get them compromised.

Keywords: Arise and Channels Televisions, Audience, political news, perception

Introduction

In recent times, the coverage of political news stories by television stations in Nigeria is said to shape public opinion (Oluwatoyin, 2023). This indicates the power associated with television medium when they go all out to cover events that affect the masses. Oluwatoyin (2023) argued that television stations in Nigeria tend to bend towards a given ideology and ethnicity in their reportage of political stories. They also tend to exhibit some level of bias towards some political parties.

On the 8th of October 2023, Amnesty International criticized the federal government for issuing a warning to Arise news television station through the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC). Arise television was accused by the NBC of using offensive and inflammatory comments in their reportage of political news stories (Akinwale, 2023). The report of TVC and the subsequent backlash from the NBC indicates the perception the people and government have over political news handling by Arise television.

In April 2023, the National Broadcasting Commission fined Channels Television the sum of five million naira for allegedly violating the National Broadcasting Code simply because the station granted a political interview to the Labour Party vice presidential candidate, Datti Baba-Ahmed on Wednesday 22nd March, 2023 during the station's flagship programme, "Politics Today" (Suleiman, 2023). The fine raised many comments among the audience of the television and Nigeria in general. The NBC accused Channels of using inciting words that were capable of heating up the polity. There were many reactions from the members of the public on the said issue which again raised issues of political news handling by television stations especially Arise and Channels Television.

Ordinarily, television stations ought to be independent of government interference. However, whenever government perceive that certain comments can lead to mixed feelings among the people, they tend to come after the media (Schennach, 2017). This is a clear indication of how political contents can lead to different perceptions among the people. In some cases, these perceptions can either be positive or negative and will go a long way to shape the opinion of the people.

In presenting political news story, it is important that the journalist consider the principle of balance and fairness. One of the cardinal hallmarks of journalism profession is balance and objectivity. As the fourth estate of the realm, the media are expected to serve as a watchdog to the government at all levels to ensure that those who hold the reins of power live up to expectations in their sacred duty of working for the good and welfare of the citizenry (Nnah, 2019, Etumnu et al., 2025). On the strength of the foregoing, the way media organizations handle news, especially those related to politics, is of the essence.

For quite a long time now, broadcasting organisations in Nigeria and even their print media counterparts have been on a greater part, dependent on funds emanating from the sale of airtime and space and sponsorship of the programmes in their various media outlets. The proclivity to use only the stories that have been paid for by clients especially political actors rather than stories that scaled through the usual news determinants usually leaves the news operators in a sort of dilemma (Zaller, 2017). They find themselves being pulled between adhering to the ethics of the journalism profession which demands fair and objective reporting and the desire to make sufficient revenue so as to make ends meet and to keep head above water in the face of a worsening economic situation in the country.

However, this habit and practices of most media outlets have again and again been leaning towards or have often resulted in sensationalizing, misleading, instigating, being insensitive or making the consumers oblivious of the issues or havocs or irregularities perpetrated by those who manage the affairs of the state. Paid adverts and commercials and especially items with political contents have indeed become the lifeblood of the Nigerian broadcast media, and this development has consequently changed news content as far as media social responsibility is concerned.

This study examined the news handling activities of two of these privately-owned electronic media outfits, Arise and Channels Television, which seem to have been commanding huge viewership. The aim here essentially was to determine how they have fared in their efforts to keep head above water in terms of keeping to the rules in the books irrespective of the challenging circumstances.

Even with the introduction of media private ownership, the criteria for news are still intact. It is true that the difference in the journalists' interpretation of a newsworthy event may sometimes bring confusion, however, there are still criteria which have evolved for the assessment of the newsworthiness of an event. Media are people who communicate with the world and humanity. Therefore, the role of media as one of the most important and sometimes limited means of informing, educating and entertaining society cannot be overemphasized. Media works in society like the effect of water on the body.

Therefore, media have witnessed many changes in the last decade due to the changes brought by electronic media in terms of reporting and presentation of information. However, although media managers may now say that they play a catalytic role or see the role of the watchdog in their products, it is imperative for media professionals to draw a line between their work and their commitment to social responsibilities.

This is the essence of this study: to investigate the audience perception of political news produced by two media outlets in Nigeria, Arise and Channels Television.

Statement of the Problem

Nigerian media environment over the years was originally in the hands of both the Federal and the State governments with the State-owned broadcast media engaged in commercial broadcasting as well as public service broadcasting and with the majority of its news contents aimed at promoting the policies and programmes of the government. Apart from paid advertisements or commercials, sponsored political news or similar contents seem to have long become the lifeblood of the Nigerian broadcast media, and this

development has consequently changed news content as far as media social responsibility is concerned. The social responsibility function of the media seems no longer obtainable in Nigeria media organisations and this problem has continued to linger over the years. The objective of media ownership, which is public interest, seems being neglected, with attention probably being paid more to sponsored or paid contents, especially from the political circles.

With the way political news stories are handled in Nigeria by most broadcast media houses, there are tendencies that some television stations may have been allowing themselves to be compromised by politicians to allow them have access to their broadcast media space. This may be the reason why some of the political news programmes tend to favour the political party involved or focused on in some cases. There are instances where politicians on Arise or Channels televisions have made utterances that received backlash from the people and in some other cases, the stations are slammed with sanctions from National Broadcasting Commission. These problems are common during electioneering period.

It has been observed that market-driven concerns have marginalized minority viewpoints and undermined the exercise of a genuine pluralism of opinions in the news production of some broadcast stations. Actors in the political space have capitalised on this and broadcast media organisations have become pun in the hands of politicians. Because of this, some people now think that most media organisations were established for profit motive and to serve the interest of the powerful few in the corridors of power instead of general human interest. This narrative remains unabated despite efforts for change in this direction.

The crux of the study therefore was to find out if and to what extent Arise and Channels Television Stations do things differently in this regard or whether they are operating in keeping with the same narrative of receiving some financial or other inducements and allowing some political actors to dictate the tune of their news content.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to examine public perception of political news handling in Arise and Channels Televisions, with focus on residents of Enugu metropolis. The specific objectives of this study, therefore, were to:

1. Ascertain the level of exposure of the residents of Enugu metropolis to Arise and Channels televisions news programmes
2. Determine the knowledge level of residents of Enugu metropolis on the news presentation styles of Arise and Channel Televisions
3. Ascertain the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis on political news presentation of Arise and Channels televisions.
4. Determine the influence of Arise and Channels television styles of political news presentation on the preference of the residents of Enugu metropolis.
5. Identify the factors that influence the perception of the residents of Enugu metropolis of Arise and Channels television political news presentations.

Literature Review

Arise News Television

Arise News is a London-based world news channel established in 2013. It has studios in New York City, London, Johannesburg, Abuja and Lagos. The channel features African, US and European contents. It is operated by Arise Broadcasting Ltd., which is owned by the Nigerian media mogul, Nduka Obaigbena.

As of October 2017, Arise News is available on Channel 416 on DStv in Nigeria. As of June 2020, Arise News can be found streaming on Freeview via its own service on Channel 269 and as part of

the Visiontv line-up on Channel 264. Arise also runs a second channel on Visiontv. called Live 360. This channel is more focused on entertainment with fashion shows similar to the ones on Fashion TV and Edgy TV, and sports, with greyhound racing broadcast on the channel until 2021 (when Sporty Stuff HD on Freesat channel 250 took over the rights).

On 9 February 2022, the company rebranded Live 360 as Arise Play, the same name as the company's Nigerian streaming platform. The Arise Play service was launched in 2021 and has a number of titles from BBC Studios in its catalogue, with productions such as *Luther*, Steve McQueen's *Small Axe*, *Famalam*, *The First Team*, David Olusoga's *Britain: A Forgotten History* and *Hey Duggee* available to Nigerian subscribers. (Source: <https://www.arise.tv>)

Channels Television

Channels Television is a multiple award winning 24-hour news and media organization which was founded in 1992 by Nigerian veteran broadcasters and business moguls: John Momoh and Sola Momoh. The Company commenced operations in Lagos, South Western Nigeria and has since grown to include three other Stations in Abuja, Edo and Kano states. The Company also has bureaus in almost every state in Nigeria, including stringers and affiliates in other parts of Africa.

Operating in Nigeria's hugely popular broadcast media market, Channels Television was the first thriving national TV brand, dedicated solely to the dissemination of news.

According to the information available in the official website of the outfit, Channels TV was established with the aim of cultivating and upholding the highest ideals in reporting the news with objectivity and fairness, as well as satisfying the right of the individual to be informed. The Company was licensed in June 1993 and allocated a frequency on UHF (channel 39). It began transmission two years later under the name, "Channels Television", and now broadcasts to a well discerning audience of over 20 million people. The Station has earned a reputation as an aggressive news outlet, which provides a balanced account of news coverage.

The establishment of Channels Television as a news station was in response to the yearning of Nigerians for a TV Station that will among other things: Give an alternative medium of communication to the government and its policies, and hold public officers accountable to the people; Accommodate opposing views; Inform and educate the general public on how they are governed, as well as educate them on their civic responsibilities to the state; Uphold the ideals of balanced reporting, objectivity, fairness and the right of the individual to be informed. Committed to presenting the news with proven facts; Airing divergent views, irrespective of differences and circumstances. Airing news that affects Nigerians and ensuring that the people are given a voice

Channels TV takes enormous pride in its role of an unbiased, candid observer of events in Nigeria, and its indisputable position today, as market leader, in its chosen but exclusive sphere, is an eloquent testimony to its unceasing innovativeness and remarkable evolution. The Company is home to award-winning and outstanding broadcasters and that has remained one of its key strengths.

Channels is the market leader in independent news in Nigeria. BBG-Gallup research shows Channels attracts 17% of Nigeria's adult population weekly, or nearly 20 million people. Channels has received the Best Television Station of the Year" award from the Nigerian Media Merit Award Trust for a record fifteen of the last twenty years, the last award of which was in December, 2022.

It was the first Nigerian and African media organization to stream its news and programs live, the first and only TV station in Nigeria with over 1,000,000 YouTube subscribers, and the first and only TV company in Nigeria with almost 7,000,000 social media followers, fans, and subscribers. Its flagship programs, *News at Ten*, *Sunrise Daily* and *Politics Today* are among the most popular and the most watched television programmes in the Country. (Source: <https://www.channelstv.com>)

Politics and Political News

As defined by the Oxford online Dictionary, politics refers to the activities associated with the governance of a country or area, especially the debate between parties having power. It also refers to activities aimed at improving someone's status or increasing power within an organization.

Political news refers basically to news produced especially by the mainstream media, such as newspaper, radio or news television channel, that contains information related with politics, public issues and matters related to governance and organization of a given state or country (*Source: igi-global.com*).

Empirical Review

Sangwon and Michael (2022) study aimed at investigating the causal direction of the relationship between incidental news exposure via social media and political participation. Unlike prior studies, which have relied on cross-sectional data to examine this link, we used two panel data sets to better identify causal relationships. The findings reveal a more complex relationship than most previous studies have suggested.

The relationship between incidental news exposure via social media and political participation appears to be reciprocal, with incidental news exposure and political participation indirectly influencing each other through social media use for political purposes. Furthermore, while the relationship between incidental news exposure and political participation is reciprocal, the participation-to-incidental news exposure path exerted a stronger effect than the reverse path in both studies.

According to Olaniru et al. (2020), this study examined the frequency of the forms of media accessed and level of political knowledge among Nigerian students. It also assessed the relationships between political knowledge and access to radio, television, newspaper, and social media. Moreover, it investigated the predictive influence of the frequency of media access on Nigerian students' political knowledge. Using cross-sectional survey research design, a structured questionnaire was used to collect information on students' demographic. Findings identified social media as the most frequently use media, followed by radio, television and newspaper. 31% of the respondents had very high political knowledge while 3% had no political knowledge. Access to radio is the only significant correlate ($r = 0.42, p$).

Oluwalanu et al. (2022) in their study sought to find out audience perception of news credibility as it pertains to TV news presentations. Findings also indicated that the majority of respondents agreed that female news presenters were more appealing and casted more than their male counterparts for their looks but disagreed that the gender of a news presenter had any connection to their perception of the news credibility. The study also indicated that other aesthetics and personality elements that could influence perception as voice, eloquence of the presenter and the news content.

Sabigan (2007) on the credibility perceptions of television and online news noted that three main factors influence the public's perception of television and online news media. This study found that reporters' credibility, media credibility, and news credibility had direct influence on the credibility of news presented on both media. Reporters' credibility on both media could be measured by their expertise, intelligence, education, trustworthiness, and authoritativeness. Television and the internet were evaluated differently. Television was measured by its comprehensiveness, concern for the interest of the public, and fairness. The internet was assessed on its trustworthiness, consideration of public interest, and objectivity. News credibility for both media, however, could be evaluated using the same measures such as news trustworthiness and objectivity.

Using focus group discussions, Acquaye and Ofori-Boateng (2021) sought to understand how media audiences perceive information in the media environment in Ghana. The study found out that the prevalence of fake news on social media platforms serves as a disincentive to consumers of media messages from giving attention to information from some media platforms. Legacy media, radio and television, for many of the participants, present credible information on its platform with the belief that rigorous scrutiny is done by the media organisation before information is shared with their audiences on air. Though

participants in the group discussions are often dismissive of media information they have doubts about, they occasionally, not routinely, verify information from news portals they deem credible. Participants also rely on their intuition to assess the truthfulness or otherwise of a story.

The purpose of Nzeji (2014) study was to investigate audience perception on coverage of political news programmes of Africa Independent Television (AIT) in Enugu metropolis Enugu state using survey method. Results showed that audience attach importance to the status and pedigree of African Independent Television (AIT) hence influences their perception and believes and in the way they react to certain issues of life and act as a watchdog over the government. Finally, the survey revealed that African Independent Television (AIT) political news coverage is of good quality, timely, precise and detailed political news programs.

Mehrabi et al. (2009) in their study on news media credibility of the internet and television used a survey to identify factors that influence media perception to determine how participants view the internet and television in terms of news media credibility. A survey was conducted among 270 non-academic professionals to identify factors affecting perceptions of media credibility. Systematic sampling method was used in sample selection. The results of the study showed that television is more reliable in providing information than the internet. This study also found a significant relationship between stress, media addiction and media use, and safe internet and television access.

Igben and Oronukpo (2022) examined the influence of news credibility on the corporate image of broadcast media in Nigeria. The paper was anchored on the preliminary assumption that a relationship exists between the credibility of the news a media disseminated and how the public perceives it. Source Credibility Theory and Perception Theory were used as its theoretical framework. A Survey of 375 respondents, the eventual outcome of distributed 400 copies of the questionnaire provided evidence that the public confidence in government owned broadcast media is low compared to the private broadcast media as a direct consequence of the level of credibility of the news they disseminate.

Arede and Oji (2022) investigated the impact of radio broadcasting on political participation in Nigeria's South-South Zone. The importance of radio in political participation has been proven by scholars. Thus, this study builds on the success of radio in this area to ascertain if the same result can be replicated in South-South, Nigeria. The study is anchored on a cross-sectional research design and surveyed 400 respondents. Findings of the study reaffirmed the position of scholars on the subject of investigation, indicating that South-South peoples' behaviour towards political activities is strongly affected by radio broadcast.

Igben and Oronukpo (2022) study examined the influence of news credibility on the corporate image of broadcast media in Nigeria. For this study while the survey research method was adopted in the collection of quantitative data. Results revealed that 71.4% had access to development programmes through radio and television, while 36% preferred radio as the medium for access. Radio remained a popular medium for disseminating development messages in Nigeria. In addition, majority of the respondents indicated that media programmes encourage participation in national development.

Utalor (2019) the study examined perceived impact of broadcast media messages on knowledge, attitude and perception of maternal health among women in Ilorin. Survey method was used. The findings of this study revealed that women in Ilorin depend mostly on broadcast media as a major source of information on maternal health but they identified radio as more effective than television in disseminating maternal health messages (58.2). Further findings also revealed that women agreed to the statement that broadcast media positively change their attitude towards maternal health ($M=1.9$, $SD=1.1$).

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted two theories that were used as theoretical framework for the study with the aim of explaining the variables and to anchor, guide and deepen the understanding of this study. These theories were Source Credibility Theory and Perception Theory.

Source Credibility Theory

Source credibility theory which was propounded in 1963 by Hovland, Janis and Kelly holds that an audience or receivers of information are more likely to be persuaded when the source of that information presents itself as credible.

Source Credibility is a fundamental concept in the field of communication and psychology that aims to understand how individuals perceive the credibility of information sources. The theory suggests that the perceived credibility of a source significantly influences the extent to which people accept, believe, and act upon the information provided by that source.

According to source credibility theory, there are two key components that contribute to the perceived credibility of a source: expertise and trustworthiness. Expertise refers to the perceived knowledge, qualifications, and experience of the source in a particular subject area. A source is considered more credible if they are perceived to be knowledgeable and competent in the relevant field. Trustworthiness, on the other hand, refers to the perceived honesty, integrity, and reliability of the source. A trustworthy source is more likely to be perceived as credible than one that is seen as untrustworthy.

Several factors can influence the perceived credibility of a source. These factors include the source's reputation, credentials, past behaviour, presentation style, and perceived motives. For example, a source with a history of accurate information and unbiased reporting is more likely to be perceived as credible than a source with a reputation for spreading misinformation or bias.

The concept of source credibility theory is particularly relevant in today's digital age, where information is readily available from a wide range of sources, including social media, websites, and online platforms. With the proliferation of fake news and misinformation, understanding source credibility is crucial for individuals to make informed decisions and discern the reliability of the information they encounter.

Source credibility theory provides valuable insights into how individuals evaluate and trust information sources. By considering the expertise and trustworthiness of a source, people can make more informed judgments about the credibility of the information they receive, ultimately leading to more effective communication and decision-making.

On the strength of this theory and in the context of the current study which aimed to investigate audience perception of political news handling of two television broadcast stations, the level of credence the audience would attach to the political news contents of the stations under study, is dependent on the level of their perceived credibility.

Perception Theory

Perception Theory, propounded by Berelson and Steiner in 1964, assumes that the audience pays attention to the contents of the media, learn the content of the message and make appropriate changes in their attitudes or beliefs.

Perception theory focuses on how individuals interpret and make sense of the sensory information they receive from the environment. It encompasses a wide range of research and theoretical perspectives from psychology, cognitive science, neuroscience, communication and philosophy.

Key points in perception theory include:

1. **Sensory Processing:** Perception theory explores how sensory stimuli are detected, attended to, and processed by the brain. This involves understanding how sensory organs (such as the eyes, ears, and skin) receive information and how this information is transmitted to the brain for interpretation.
2. **Perceptual Organization:** The theory of perception examines how the brain organizes and interprets sensory information to form a coherent perception of the world. This includes processes such as grouping similar elements together, distinguishing figure from ground, and filling in missing information to create a meaningful perceptual experience.
3. **Perceptual Constancy:** Perception theory also addresses the concept of perceptual constancy, which refers to the ability to perceive objects as stable and consistent despite changes in sensory input (e.g., perceiving a red apple as red under different lighting conditions).
4. **Depth Perception:** Understanding how we perceive depth and three-dimensional space is another important aspect of perception theory. This includes research on cues such as binocular disparity, motion parallax, and linear perspective that help us perceive depth and distance.
5. **Perceptual Illusions:** Perception theory also investigates perceptual illusions, which are discrepancies between sensory information and our perceptual experience. By studying these illusions, researchers gain insights into the mechanisms underlying perception and the limitations of our sensory systems.
6. **Top-Down Processing:** Perception theory emphasizes the role of top-down processing, which involves using prior knowledge, expectations, and context to interpret sensory information. This highlights the dynamic interplay between bottom-up (sensory-driven) and top-down (knowledge-driven) processes in perception.
7. **Applications:** Research in perception theory has practical implications in various fields, including psychology, design, human-computer interaction, and marketing. Understanding how people perceive and interpret information can inform the design of products, interfaces, and environments to enhance user experience and communication effectiveness.

Overall, perception theory provides valuable insights into how our sensory systems work, how we construct our perception of the world, and how our experiences and expectations influence our interpretation of sensory information. By studying perception, researchers seek to unravel the complexities of human cognition and behaviour.

The relevance of this theory to the study is that it explains how people react to media messages as a result of their perception of their handling of political news contents. In essence, different members of the audience can watch Arise and Channels television and arrive at different conclusions in the way these media houses present their political stories. This theory is also employed in the current study given the fact that people's perception of reality is usually as a result of their interpretation of the message they receive which has a lot to do with the manner the message is communicated.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted the mixed method research design, which is the mixture of quantitative and qualitative methods for the interpretation and understanding of data (Creswell & Clark, 2017). The mixed method entails the combination of quantitative design (survey) and one qualitative design (in-depth interview).

This means that the survey method was used for the quantitative aspect of the mixed method, while in-depth interview was used for the qualitative aspect of the mixed method. The reason for the choice of survey is because people's opinions were sourced through the collection of primary data from a large

number of people. A “survey method is a process, tool, or technique that you can use to gather information in research by asking questions to a predefined group of people” (Longe, 2024).

The in-depth interview method which provided the avenue for generating qualitative data aided the clarification of the findings of the quantitative data.

Tools for Data Collection

Two tools were employed in the conduct of this research and that included questionnaire which was administered to the residents of Enugu metropolis and in-depth interview conducted among members of staff of the two broadcast stations. The questionnaire instrument was designed using the four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The interview guide, on the other hand, is made up of ten items including the follow up questions. It comprised of leading questions and follow up questions aimed at eliciting more information from the respondents. The interview guide was constructed with questions that can attract additional data to clarify the data that was elicited from the questionnaire.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered all copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in the selected areas of coverage. Then the completed copies of the questionnaire were collected on the spot after administration. This was to ensure that the total number of copies of questionnaire that was administered equally tallied with the number that was retrieved. Moreover, it gave the researcher the opportunity to be present to answer any oral question from respondents and gave evidence within the confines of research ethics where necessary.

The interview was done with the combination of phone calls and face-to-face interview. Some of the staff answered the interviewed questions through phone calls. The rest were done on face-to-face basis.

Population of the Study

The population of this study are residents of Enugu metropolis who are audience of both Arise and Channels TV. This population frame is considered because both stations enjoy wide viewership particularly in the urban areas where the greater percentage of the populace is elite and has access to cable television. According to the census outcome made available to the researcher, by the National Population Commission, the population of Enugu metropolis is 717, 291, (National Population Commission (NPC), 2006).

This population which is for the quantitative aspect of the study was projected by the 2.8% growth rate of the NPC and the 18 years interval that has elapsed since the time of the last census. Therefore, $717,291 * 2.8\% * 18 = 361,515$. This value is added to the census to arrive at the current population ($717,291 + 361,515 = 1,078,806$) which is 1,078,806.

The population for the qualitative aspect of the study consist of staff of Arise and Channels TV. The population of the staff in these selected television stations are estimated to be 552, with Channels TV estimated to be having 380 staff, while Arise TV estimated to be having 172 staff (Sourced from the front desk of the two television stations).

Sample and Sampling Technique

For the quantitative aspect of the study, the sample size used for this study is 330. The researcher used Australian Online Sample Size calculator. The sample size for in-depth interview of the study was ten (10) respondents drawn from the two (2) television stations which are Arise and Channels televisions. Five (5) respondents representing each television stations. The justification for selecting ten (10) respondents is to avoid cases of redundancy and saturation (Hennink& Kaiser, 2022).

To effectively test all the variables in this study and give every element in the population an equal chance of being selected, the researcher used multi-stage sampling technique. This technique called for the use of several sampling methods or stages of a particular method in ensuring true representation. First, the researcher approached the population from the cluster point of view since Enugu metropolis is naturally divided in clusters/areas. The following clusters or areas exist in the metropolis: Uwani, Achara Layout, Agbani Road, Gariki, Coal Camp, GRA, Independence Layout, New Haven, Ogui New Layout, New Market, Old Park, Abakpa Nike, Nike Lake Road, Trans-Ekulu and Emene.

The researcher further used systematic random sampling technique to systematically select six clusters/areas at an interval of two. At the end of this selection process, the following clusters/area; Uwani, Gariki, Abakpa Nike, Emene, New Haven, Coal Camp, were selected. Systematic random sampling technique is also used to select households in each of these areas/clusters in such a way that all will have an equal chance of being selected. Given the fact that the overwhelming percentage of the people living in this area are exposed to the media, a random selection is likely to yield the expected result.

For the qualitative aspect of the study, the researcher used purposive sampling technique to select five (5) staff each from the two (2) television stations. This implies that ten (10) respondents were purposively selected for the qualitative aspect of the study.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

In a bid to ensure that the items on the questionnaire and interview guide were approved, face validity was used to validate the research instruments. Hence, the supervisor and other lecturers were given sample copies of the questionnaire and interview guide to scrutinize. Their advice and corrections were taken and strictly adhered to and effected.

The reliability of the questionnaire instrument was done with the aid of test re-test reliability technique. The researcher distributed 20 copies of the instrument for the first time at Emene and thereafter collected the copies and analysed them. After a window period of two weeks, the researcher again distributed another 20 copies of the questionnaire to residents in Emene and analysed the data collected from the respondents. The data from the first distribution were correlated with the data from the second distribution using the Cronbach formula that is compatible with likert scale. The result indicated a 0.8 reliability result

As for the qualitative interview guide, the test of reliability was done with the aid of manuscript audit. Here, the interviews conducted on three (3) respondents by the researcher were transcribed and submitted to the project supervisor and two other qualitative scholars to see if the responses were in line with the questions asked. They adjudged the response to be in line with the interview question asked. This indicated that the interview guide was reliable.

Method of Data Analysis

The data that were collected through the use of questionnaire were presented in tables by using numbers, simple percentages and mean analysis. This was done to give the quantitative aspect of the study clearer understanding. As for the qualitative aspect of the study, analysis of data collected from the field was done using discussion building technique.

Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of 330 copies of questionnaire were distributed to respondents. Six (6) copies were wrongly filled and 2 copies were not returned. 322 copies were retrieved and used for this study. Hence, the analysis for this study is based on the 322 copies of the retrieved copies of the questionnaire, representing 97.6% response rate.

As for the qualitative aspect of the study, the researcher interviewed ten respondents drawn from the two television stations under investigation. The discussion building technique was used by the researcher to analyse the qualitative data generated from the respondents.

Psychographic Data

This section focused on the psychographic data of the study, the researcher made use of mean analysis. The mean analysis is made up of modified four-point Likert items which were presented in tables with abbreviations: SA (Strongly Agree) = 4; A (Agree) = 3; D (Disagree) = 2; SD (Strongly Disagree) =1. The mean analysis enables the researcher to take decision in respect of each of the Likert item raised. The decision rule was presented in italics beneath each of the table. Some of the Likert items were later presented in Likert scale in a bid to enable the researcher attain the mean average for the basis of analysis.

Research Question One: What is the level of exposure of residents of Enugu metropolis to Arise and Channels television news programmes?

Table 1: Respondents’ Responses on If They Watch TV News Programmes

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	322	100
No	-	-
Total	322	100

Data in table 1 revealed that all the respondents which constitute 322 (100%) of the respondents watch TV news programmes. This implies that residents of Enugu metropolis watch TV news programmes.

Table 2: Respondents’ Responses on how often they watch Arise and Channels TV

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Very Often	162	50.3
Often	160	49.7
Rarely	-	-
Total	322	100

Table 2 revealed that 162 (50.3%) of the respondents watch Arise and Channels TV very often. This means that Enugu metropolis residents watch Arise and Channels TV regularly.

Table 3: Respondents' Responses on Level of Exposure to Arise and Channels TV News Programmes

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Very High	159	49.4
High	150	46.6
Moderate	13	4.0
Low	-	-
Total	322	100

Data from table 3 revealed that 159 (49.4%) of the respondents are exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes. This implies that residents of Enugu metropolis are very highly exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes.

Research Question Two: What is the knowledge level of residents of Enugu metropolis on the news presentation styles of Arise and Channel TV?

Table 4:

Options	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
Arise and Channels TV engage in panel interview of prominent individuals in their news programme	171	151	-	-	3.5	Accepted
Arise and Channels TV news are usually on current issues in the country	114	168	32	8	3.2	Accepted
The journalists in Arise and Channels TV stations do discuss the news programmes that are trending in the country	106	122	77	4	2.9	Accepted
Arise and Channels TV news presenters do invite experts to present more interpretation on important news stories.	160	101	61	-	3.3	Accepted
Arise and Channels TV news programmes are balanced, objective and credible	123	121	24	54	3.0	Accepted
Grand Mean					3.2	Accepted

Table 4 indicated that with a grand mean score 3.2, the researcher decides that respondents have high knowledge of news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV. This means that residents of Enugu Metropolis have high knowledge of news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV.

Research Question Three: What is the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis on news handling of Arise and Channels television?

Table 5:

Options	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I think Arise and channels news are very reliable	162	142	16	2	3.4	Accepted
Arise and channel TV news are unbiased in their news reportage	64	179	48	31	2.9	Accepted
Arise and channels TV news programmes do not promote or support any political party	177	104	31	10	3.4	Accepted
I think Arise and channels TV programmes are commercialized	131	157	25	9	3.3	Accepted
Arise and channels news programmes are handled by professional presenters	161	131	21	9	3.4	Accepted
There is professionalism in news presentation in Arise and Channel TV	127	154	9	-	3.1	Accepted
Arise and Channels TV news programmes are objective and credible	184	126	12	-	3.5	Accepted
Arise and Channels TV level of professionalism has earned them huge fan base	131	211	25	9	3.2	Accepted
Grand Mean					3.3	Accepted

Table 5 revealed that with a grand mean score 3.3, the researcher decides that respondents have positive perception on news handling of Arise and Channels TV. This implies that residents of Enugu metropolis have positive perception towards news handling styles of Arise and Channels TV.

Research Question Four: What is the influence of Arise TV and Channels TV style of news presentation on the preference of the resident of Enugu metropolis?

Table 6:

Options	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I enjoy watching Arise and Channels TV news programme due to their news presentation	121	172	20	9	3.3	Accepted
I enjoy news programme on Arise and Channels TV as a result of the matching pictures and images to the news stories	131	211	25	9	3.2	Accepted
As a result of the unbiased reportage of news stories in Arise and Channels TV, I now believe news reports from their stations	202	117	3	-	3.6	Accepted
I watch Arise and Channels TV news as a result of the level of professionalism by their presentations	141	179	2	-	3.4	Accepted

Having followed arise and channels TV news for a while, I believe they are objective, credible and balanced in their news stories/reports	211	107	4	-	3.6	Accepted
News programme in Arise and Channel TV are timely and accurate	254	68	-	-	3.8	Accepted
Grand mean					3.5	Accepted

Table 6 revealed that with a grand mean score 3.5, the researcher decides that Arise and Channels TV style of news presentation influence the respondents. This implies Arise and Channels TV style of news presentation influence residents of Enugu metropolis.

Research Question Five: What are other factors that influence the perception of Enugu metropolis residents in Arise and Channels TV news presentations?

Table 7:

Options	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
High quality visual production influences my preference for Arise and Channel TV news programme	84	119	23	96	2.6	Accepted
The firmness of the presenters in handling news interviews influences my perception towards Arise and Channels TV news programmes	119	60	101	42	2.8	Accepted
The current nature of news programmes influences my perception towards Arise and Channels TV news handling	103	162	21	36	3.0	Accepted
The level of news interpretation in line with the realities in the society has influenced my perception of Arise and Channels T V	151	104	42	25	3.2	Accepted
The adherence to the broadcasting code has influenced my perception of Arise and Channels TV	165	64	51	42	3.1	Accepted
Grand Mean					2.9	Accepted

Table 7 revealed that with a grand mean score 2.9, the researcher decides that there are other factors that influence the perception of the respondents in Arise and Channels TV news presentation. This means that there are other factors that influence the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis in Arise and Channels TV news presentation, these factors include; high quality visual production, current nature of their news programmes, level of news interpretation and adherence to broadcasting code.

Qualitative Analysis

For the qualitative analysis, the researcher interviewed ten (10) respondents with the aim of eliciting information that will address the research questions. Five respondents were selected from Arise television, while the other five were selected from Channels television. For the purposes of analysis, the respondents were given codes as a means of identification.

S/N	Names	Codes
1	Interviewee from Arise Television	R1A
2	Interviewee from Arise Television	R2A
3	Interviewee from Arise Television	R3A
4	Interviewee from Arise Television	R4A
5	Interviewee from Arise Television	R5A
6	Interviewee from Channels Television	R1C
7	Interviewee from Channels Television	R2C
8	Interviewee from Channels Television	R3C
9	Interviewee from Channels Television	R4C
10	Interviewee from Channels Television	R5C

What is the level of exposure of residents of Enugu metropolis to Arise and Channels television news programmes?

Analysis of data indicated that the respondents were of the opinion that the viewership of their TV stations was getting prominent. They were of review that their stations try to air their news stories when the people can have access to it. “I think the way we fashion our program especially our stories in the area of politics will make our respondent to tune into it”. –R3A. The opinion of the respondent indicated that respondents were optimistic that viewers watch their TV stations.

The implication of this analysis is that respondent from these TV stations are of the view that the audience are exposed to their stations.

What is the knowledge level of residents of Enugu metropolis on the news presentation styles of arise and channels TV?

Responding to research question two, analysis of data indicated that there are different styles adopted by both arise and channels television in their handling of political news stories.

“You see we do not just allow our station to present news the conventional way. We try to alter the way we present these news stories to create some level of interest for the masses” – R4C. Similarly, another respondent said that, “there are times we present our political news stories and follow it up with interview of guest speakers who will throw more light on the issue. In other cases, we present these stories in a full bulletin. The aim is to make user that we use different styles to reach the audience” – R2A. Another respondent noted that their own style of presenting news stories has made it possible for them to have their own type of audience, “Our style of presenting our news might not be different from other stations, but I tell you that our audience like our style” – R5A.

The implication of this analysis is that it has revealed that there are different styles adopted by Arise and Channels television to present their political news to the audience. These styles include, but are not limited to straight news, presentation by an anchor, the use of invited guests to discuss political news, panel debate on political issues and special programs by a staff of the station.

What is the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis of political news handling of Arise and Channels television?

Result of data from analysis indicated that their respondents were of the view that Arise and Channels television handle their political news stories with different levels of passion. Further analysis revealed that the audience reaction to news from Arise television in some cases are intense, while in other cases, they seem to see news presentation in channels television to be intense. There are no opinions on whether any of the stations supersedes the other in terms of political news handling. “When we present our news stories, we try to ensure that we are objective as possible by sticking to the journalistic principles. Our intention is not to outwit any other person, but to satisfy our audience who look up to us for their news consumption” – R1A.

One of the respondents were of the view that, “people do think that the way we handle our political matters give us that level of maturity and makes us a better station before everyone. However, this is not our drive. Our intention is to serve the Nigerian audience to the best of our ability and to create a reliable space for ourselves. If you ask me, I think we are trying our best, and the audience we have are solidly behind us” – R4C.

The implication of this analysis is that the respondents believe that their various audience like the way they present their news stories especially in the area of politics however, they did not indicate from their responses that Arise television is better than channels television. Instead, data revealed that the audience of Arise and Channels television tend to like the way their various TV channels handle political news stories.

What is the influence of Arise TV and Channels TV style of political news presentation on the preference of the residents of Enugu metropolis

Analysis of data indicated that the handling of news by Arise and Channels television do have the power to influence the audience to prefer one television station against the other. Respondents were of the opinion that news handling by television station has power to influence the choice of TV stations that the audience listen to. Some of the respondents said they believe the audience listened to their station because their news anchors try their best to present the facts to the interest and admiration of the audience.

However, they were not able to say that it was the political news that influence the choice of the station that the audience watch. One of the respondents said that “I know that people watch television for different reasons. That is to say, they choose the station to watch based on difference in interest. However, the way we present our political programmes and news is always of interest to many of our audience. But I cannot tell you categorically that it was just the political news stories that influenced our audience to choose us. I think they must have put several things together before settling with us. Even at that, I think some people do switch between stations to get the best of the news that is trending” –R3A. this was the majority opinion of the respondents.

The implication of this finding is that respondents are not clearly certain that it was the handling of political news in these stations that influenced the choice of either Arise or Channels television station by members of the audience. They were of the opinion that other forms of news stories plus the political news might have influenced the choice of either Arise television or Channels television by the audience.

What are other factors that influence the perception of Enugu Metropolis residents of Arise and Channels television political news presentations?

Analysis of data by the respondents revealed that these are various factors that “may influence the choice or preference of television station to view by the audiences” some of the respondents were of the opinion that the quality of television programme and the sound nature of the news anchored dictates the station of viewership. There are of the opinion that if the station has good aesthetic presentation, quality technology

and good news presenters, then the viewers will make up their mind on the station to view. “I think that the audience watch our station (Channels) because of the soundness of our news handlers especially the political news presentations. They also appreciate the fact that we use better software and technology to present our news programmes” – R4C. This was almost similar to the response of one of the respondents who noted that “the intelligence of our political news handlers is one of the reason why our station is watched by the audience” – R2A.

The implication of this analysis is that it is not only the handling of the political news that influence the choice of television station to watch, but that other factors also affect the preference of television station to watch. The aesthetics quality of the television station as well as the technology employed by the stations determines the station of choice preferred by the audience.

Discussion of Findings

This aspect of discussion of findings focuses on the level of exposure of Enugu metropolis residents to Arise and Channels TV news programmes. Result from the analysis revealed that majority of the residents of Enugu metropolis which constitute 49.9% (159) are exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes. This means that residents of Enugu metropolis are highly exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes. Specifically, data revealed that 100% (322) of residents of Enugu metropolis watch TV news programmes. Also, data further revealed that 50.3% (162) of residents of Enugu metropolis regularly watch Arise and Channels TV. Analysis of interview data revealed that there is high level of exposure to Arise and Channels TV news programmes.

On the other hand, analysis of qualitative data indicated that the respondents were of the opinion that the viewership of their TV stations was getting prominent. They noted that members of the audience do watch their news programmes due to the effort they are making to get better by the day. The implication of this analysis is that respondent from these TV stations are of the view that the audience are exposed to their stations.

This implies that data from both the quantitative and qualitative analysis support the fact that residents of Enugu metropolis are exposed to Arise and Channels television stations. This finding concurs with the findings of Oluwalanu, Amos, Zechariah and Morenike (2022) which revealed that people are exposed to news programmes of various television stations. Similarly, the findings of Igben and Oronukpo (2022) revealed that audience are exposed to news programmes broadcast by television stations.

This aspect of discussion of findings focuses on the knowledge level of residents of Enugu metropolis on the news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV news programmes. Results from quantitative data analysed indicated that at an average mean of 3.2, residents of Enugu metropolis have high knowledge of news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV. Specifically, with a mean score of 3.5, residents of Enugu metropolis agree that Arise and Channels TV engage in panel interview of prominent individuals in their news programme. Also, with a mean score of 3.2, residents of Enugu Metropolis agree that Arise and Channels TV news are usually on current issues of the nation. Furthermore, with a mean score of 2.9, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that journalists in Arise and Channels TV stations discuss news programmes that are trending in the country.

Similarly, with a mean score of 3.3, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TV news presenters invite experts to present more interpretation on important news stories. Also, with a mean score of 3.0, residents of Enugu metropolis opined that Arise and Channels TV news programmes are balanced, objective and credible. Analysis of interview data revealed that residents of Enugu metropolis have high knowledge of news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV.

Responding to research question two, analysis of qualitative data indicated that there are different styles adopted by both Arise and Channels television in their handling of political news stories. The implication of this analysis is that it has revealed that there are different styles adopted by Arise and Channels television to present their political news to the audience. These styles include, but are not limited

to straight news, presentation by an anchor, the use of invited guests to discuss political news, panel debate on political issues and special programs by a staff of the station.

Result from data analysis indicated that there are indeed different styles adopted by Arise and Channel television in the presentation of their political news stories. These style ranges from direct news presentation to panel discussions. These findings is corroborated by that of Olaniru, Olatunji, Ayandele, and Popoola (2020) who noted that knowledge about politics and government activities increases due to the socialization and enlightenment functions of the mass media.

This also found that radio and television were among the media that created very high political knowledge among the audience. Similarly, Sanusi, Daniel, Olanihun, and Olanrewaju, (2022). Attributed that success of television in creating political knowledge to the style of their presentation through the use of appealing presenters. They noted that female news presenters were more appealing and casted more than their male counterparts for their looks.

This aspect of discussion of findings focuses on the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis on the news handling of Arise and Channels televisions. Data analysed revealed that with an average mean of 3.3, residents of Enugu metropolis perceive Arise and Channels TV to be reliable, credible, professional and unbiased in the handling of political news stories. Specifically, with a mean score of 3.4, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TV news are very reliable. Also, with a mean score of 2.9, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TV news are unbiased in their news reportage. Furthermore, with a mean score of 3.4, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that news programmes by Arise and Channels TV don't support and promote any political party. Similarly, with a means score of 3.3, residents of Enugu metropolis don't think Arise and Channels TV programmes are commercialized.

Further analysis revealed that with a mean score of 3.4, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TV news programmes are handled by professional presenters. Also, with a means score of 3.1, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that there is professionalism in news presentation in Arise and Channels TV. Similarly, with a means score of 3.5, residents of Enugu metropolis agree that Arise and Channels TV news programmes are objective and credible. Also, with a means score of 3.2, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TVs level of professionalism has earned them a huge fan base. Analysis of interview data revealed that residents of Enugu metropolis have positive perception towards news handling styles of Arise and Channels TVs.

Result from qualitative data indicated that Arise and Channels television present their political news stories with different levels of passion. Further analysis revealed that the audience reaction to news from Arise television in some cases are intense, while in other cases, they seem to see news presentation in channels television to be preferable. There are no opinions on whether any of the stations supersedes the other in terms of political news handling. The implication of this analysis is that the respondents believe that their various audience like the way they present their news stories especially in the area of politics however, they did not indicate from their responses that Arise television is better than channels television. Instead, data revealed that the audience of Arise and Channels television tend to like the way their various TV channels handle political news stories.

Supporting the findings of this study, Igben and Oronukpo (2022) noted that people prefer to listen and watch private stations than the public television because the private station are seen to be more credible. They noted that the public confidence in government owned broadcast media is low compared to the private broadcast media. There is a high level of confidence in the credibility of the news disseminated by private media houses.

Similarly, Acquaye and Ofosu-Boateng (2021) found that legacy media (radio and television), for many of the participants, present credible information on its platform with the belief that rigorous scrutiny is done by the media organisation before information is shared with their audiences on air. This finding is also in line with that of Nzeji, (2014) which revealed that audience attach importance to the status and pedigree of African Independent Television (AIT) hence influences their perception and believes and in the way they react to certain issues of life and act as a watchdog over the government.

This aspect of discussion of findings focuses on the influence of Arise and Channels TV style of news presentation on the preference of the residents of Enugu metropolis. Data analysed revealed that, with an average mean of average mean score 2.9, Arise and Channels televisions style of news presentation influence residents of Enugu metropolis. Specifically, with a mean score of 3.3, residents of Enugu metropolis enjoy watching news programmes on Arise and Channels TV due to their style of news presentation. Also, with a means score of 3.2, result of the matching pictures and images to news stories, residents of Enugu metropolis enjoy news programmes.

Furthermore, with a means score of 3.6, Arise and Channels TV unbiased reportage of news stories made residents of Enugu metropolis to believe in news reports from their stations. Similarly, with a means score of 3.4, Arise and Channels TV level of professionalism in presentation made the residents of Enugu metropolis watch their news programme. Further analysis revealed that with a mean score of 3.6, residents of Enugu metropolis believe that Arise and Channels TV news stories/reports are objective, credible and balance. Also, with a means score of 3.8, residents of Enugu metropolis affirm that Arise and Channels TV news programmes are timely and accurate.

Result of data from the qualitative analysis indicated that the handling of news by Arise and Channels television do have the power to influence the audience to prefer one television station against the other. Respondents were of the opinion that news handling by television station has power to influence the choice of TV stations that the audience listen to. The implication of this findings is that respondents are not clearly certain that it was the handing of political news in these stations that influenced the choice of either Arise or Channels television station by members of the audience. They were of the opinion that other forms of news stories plus the political news might have influenced the choice of either Arise television or Channels television by the audience.

The result of the qualitative data was more obvious in establishing that the style of news presentation by Arise and Channels television influenced the choice of television station preference by the audience. Although, finding did not single out political news presentation as the major factor that influenced that choice of station to watch. This is the same with the quantitative data which did not show that it was the political news that influenced the audience choice of television station to watch. By implication, people might be influenced by television programmes but not necessarily by the political news programmes.

The findings of this study is in consonance with that of Arede and Oji (2022) who found that listening to political news programme do influence the people to act in a certain way. They noted that South-South peoples' behaviour towards political activities is strongly affected by radio broadcast. In the same vein, Akoja (2016) noted that radio and television programme do have the propensity to influence the people to take part in government programme. They noted that radio remained a popular medium for disseminating development messages in Nigeria.

In addition, majority of the respondents indicated that media programmes encourage participation in national development. Utalor (2019) also found out that broadcast media do have influence on the knowledge, attitude and behaviour of women in the area of maternal health. The findings of this study revealed that women in Ilorin depend mostly on broadcast media as a major source of information on maternal health but they identified radio as more effective than television in disseminating maternal health messages (58.2). further findings also revealed that women agreed to the statement that broadcast media positively change their attitude towards maternal health.

This aspect of discussion of findings focuses on the other factors that influence the perception of Enugu metropolis residents in Arise and Channels TV news presentation. Data analysed revealed that with an average mean score 2.9, there are other factors that influence the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis in Arise and Channels TV news presentation, these factors include; high quality visual production, current nature of their news programmes, level of news interpretation and adherence to broadcasting code.

Specifically, with a means score of 2.6, the availability of female beauty brands products influences the patronage of these products by female Facebook users in Southeast. Also, with a means score of 2.8,

firmness of the presenters in handling news interviews influences the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis towards Arise and Channels TV news programmes. Furthermore, with a means score of 3.0, the current nature of news programmes influences the residents of Enugu metropolis perception towards Arise and Channels TV news handling.

Similarly, with a means score of 3.2, the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis towards Arise and Channels TV is influenced by news interpretation in line with the realities in the society. Also, with a means score of 3.1, adherence to the broadcasting code has influenced residents of Enugu metropolis perception of Arise and Channels TV. Analysis of interview data revealed that there are other factors that influence the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis in Arise and Channels TV news presentation, some these factors are high quality visual production, current nature of their news programmes, level of news interpretation and adherence to broadcasting code.

Analysis of data by the respondents revealed that these are various factors that may influence the choice or preference of television station to view by the audiences. Some of the respondents were of the opinion that the quality of television programme and the sound nature of the news anchored dictates the station of viewership.

There are of the opinion that if the station has good aesthetic presentation, quality technology and good news presenters, then the viewers will make up their mind on the station to view. The implication of this analysis is that it is not only the handling of the political news that influence the choice of television station to watch, but that other factors also affect the preference of television station to watch. The aesthetics quality of the television station as well as the technology employed by the stations determines the station of choice preferred by the audience.

This finding is in corroboration with that of Sabigan (2007) which revealed that reporters' credibility, media credibility, and news credibility are factors that influence the perception of the audiences in regards to news presentation. Similarly, Mehrabi, Abu and Sham (2009) revealed that television is a factor that is more credible to convey news. Furthermore, Oluwalanu et al. (2022) indicated that other aesthetics and personality elements such as the voice and eloquence of the presenter contributed heavily to the choice of television station the audience would prefer to watch.

Conclusion

This study examined the perception of Enugu metropolis residents towards political news handling in Arise and Channels TV. The researcher concludes that residents of Enugu metropolis are exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes. Also, residents of Enugu metropolis have high knowledge of news presentation styles of Arise and Channels TV. Furthermore, residents of Enugu metropolis have positive perception towards political news handling styles of Arise and Channels TV. This implies that Arise and Channels TV political news presentation styles made people have positive perception about the stations.

The researcher further concludes that residents of Enugu metropolis are influenced by Arise and Channels TV styles of political news presentation. Furthermore, there are other factors that influence the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis in Arise and Channels TV political news presentation. These factors include: high quality visual production, current nature of their news programmes, level of news interpretation, the personality of the presenter and adherence to broadcasting code.

Recommendations

1. Giving that analysis of findings revealed that residents of Enugu metropolis are highly exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes, the researcher therefore recommends that management of Arise and Channels TV should continue broadcasting political news programmes.
2. Considering the fact that quantitative analysis (average mean score of 3.2) showed that residents of Enugu metropolis have high knowledge of political news presentation styles of Arise and Channels

TV, the researcher recommends that Arise and Channels TV should maintain and continue to improve their political news presentation styles.

3. Findings of the study indicated that with average mean of 3.3, residents of Enugu metropolis have positive perception towards political news handling styles of Arise and Channels TV, the researcher recommends that Arise and Channels TV should continue to apply creativity in their political news handling styles in a bid to maintain and improve the perception by their audience.
4. Communicating findings from the field indicated that with an average mean score 2.9, Arise and Channels TV style of political news presentation influence residents of Enugu metropolis, the researcher recommends that Arise and Channels TV should maintain their style of political news presentation due to its influence on their audience.
5. Data analysed revealed that with an average mean score 2.9, there are other factors that influence the perception of residents of Enugu metropolis in Arise and Channels TV political news presentation, the researcher recommends that the stations should remain neutral in their presentation, interpretation and the nature of their political news programmes and resist any attempt to be compromised by political actors.

Limitations of the Study and Contribution to Knowledge

The study was restricted to the opinions from the copies of questionnaire shared to the audience of Arise and Channels media stations. Also, an oral interview was conducted with some of the media employees of these two stations. The study was also limited by time available to carry out the research. The available time was not adequate given that several other activities had to be scheduled within the same period.

This study has brought to limelight the fact that residents of Enugu metropolis are sufficiently exposed to Arise and Channels TV news programmes and that they possess a positive perception toward the political news handling of Arise and Channels TV broadcast stations.

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